

Deliverable

D4.5 Results of three workshops with ethics committees and research integrity bodies

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1. Executive Summary

Throughout the course of the PRO-Ethics project, it has been vital to engage with the wealth of expertise that exists in the field of research ethics and integrity. Although this project is developing something novel in the form of an ethical framework to guide the principles and activities of research and innovation funding organisations with respect to participation in their processes, it is also building on a huge amount of existing knowledge and practice in related fields.

PRO-Ethics task 4.3, *Dialogue with ethics committees and research integrity bodies*, was designed to gather insights, reflection and feedback from research ethics committees (RECs) and research integrity offices (RIOs). The overall goal of this task is to build a community of ethics and integrity experts that are engaged in the progress and outputs of PRO-Ethics. Our aim in this was twofold. First, we wanted to identify and engage organisations and individuals who could contribute their expertise to the development of the pilots and ethical framework. Second, we intended to provide these stakeholders with useful learning and case studies to develop their own practices and resources to support the institutions they serve.

The workshops organised for this task aimed to serve the needs of the external stakeholders invited to participate, in addition to supporting the learning and iteration of activities led by the wider PRO-Ethics consortium. This report summarises the key lessons learnt from research ethics and integrity experts engaged, explains how insights were embedded in the development of PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines and reflects on wider lessons from delivery of this task.

2. Introduction

PRO-Ethics is working with research and innovation funding organisations across Europe to test new, ethical ways to involve citizens in three fields of action: participation in innovation projects, participation in strategy development and participation in evaluation processes. PRO-Ethics will deliver an ethics framework, together with a set of practical guidelines and actionable criteria for assessing the quality and ethics of participation processes.

Task 4.3 ran from month 6 of the PRO-Ethics project (June 2020) to month 39 (March 2023). Over this time, PRO-Ethics partners delivering this task (Nesta, EUREC and EUREKA) carried out interviews and working sessions with representatives from research ethics committees (RECs) and research integrity offices (RIOs), and organised a total of four interactive workshops – one targeted only towards RECs, one towards RIOs, bookended by two workshops engaging the entire community. D4.3 reported on the first phase of this work, including a series of interviews carried out with experts, and an interactive online workshop held in M9 (September 2020).

This report gives an update on engagement activities with this group of key stakeholders that have occurred since M9, and shares results from the second interactive workshop with research ethics and integrity experts, as well as the two additional workshops that were designed and delivered to deepen the links between PRO-Ethics and the community of ethics committees and research integrity bodies, respectively.

3. Activities

3.1 Workshops with research ethics and integrity experts

The final formal engagement activities with representatives of research ethics and integrity communities were designed to ensure that their input could meaningfully shape the design of the final PRO-Ethics framework and ethical guidelines. The events were also intended to create opportunities for mutual learning, and inform the development of ethics guidelines being developed in other fields.

Workshop with Research Ethics Committees (June 2022)

This workshop was conceived and implemented by PRO-Ethics partner EUREC Office and invited 25 representatives of research ethics committees from different European countries to discuss participation in R&I from the perspective of research ethics. Homing in on the ethical considerations arising at the intersection between RECs, researchers and the public, the workshop focused on two key questions:

- ▶ What is the responsibility of RECs with regard to community engagement?
- ▶ What do REC members need to consider when they involve lay people in ethical review processes?

Both questions were discussed in a lively world café session, which revealed that RECs need advice on when and how to involve lay people in ethical reviews. Another important issue for RECs in terms of ethics and participation is the 'social value of research'. Research and innovation aim to create new knowledge that benefits our society. When reviewing research projects, RECs may need to consider whether a research project has social value. However, the question is what benefits our society and how to balance individual and social value. RECs could use advice on how to proceed here. The results of the workshop were shared with partners and fed into discussions about revisions of the PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines.

Workshop with members of Research Integrity Offices and other RI experts (September 2022)

This workshop was designed to create space for consideration of key questions that were beginning to emerge through the process of developing the Ethics Framework. Representatives of research integrity community were brought together at a time when the activities of research funding organisations (RFOs) within the PRO-Ethics consortia had begun to confront challenges. Key questions this community of experts were asked to consider were:

- ▶ How does the participation of citizens and other non-traditional stakeholders support good scientific practice?
- ▶ To what extent can citizens be equal partners in the research and innovation process?
- ▶ How could ideas and principles relating to citizen participation be integrated within the ALLEA Code of Conduct, and other similar research integrity frameworks?

Through an interactive workshop a select group of experts from the field of ethics and research integrity, alongside organisations in the PRO-Ethics consortium discussed these questions and generated ideas.

The idea was to allow for mutually beneficial learning that would inform the work of both PRO-Ethics and research integrity bodies themselves.

Workshop with RECs and RIOs: Consultation on the PRO-Ethics Framework (January 2023)

This final workshop brought together research ethics and research integrity experts once more, and was an opportunity for PRO-Ethics to gather specific comments on the practical guidelines being developed for use by research funding organisations across the world. Having direct feedback on the guidelines was extremely important to make use of the immense knowledge that experts in these fields have related to the involvement of citizens in research activities. Key questions considered included:

- ▶ How can PRO-Ethics guidelines integrate and build on existing research ethics and integrity codes of conduct?
- ▶ What opportunities exist to continue collaborating and sharing lessons and best practice on how to involve citizens in research and science funding activities?

The session was broken up into small groups to allow for deep conversations on each of the provocations presented, and a detailed presentation of the PRO-Ethics ethical framework in its current version was provided in order to introduce all experts to the framework.

3.2 Other engagement with the research ethics and integrity communities

Alongside the formal activities and deliverables associated with this Task 4.3, PRO-Ethics partners have sought other opportunities - both formal and informal - to share the ongoing work around the development of the ethics framework with the wider research ethics and integrity communities.

The first draft of the ethics framework was based on extensive interviews with research ethics committees and research integrity bodies, while the final version was tested with these same experts to iterate before completion.

PRO-Ethics has also been presented at a number of relevant meetings, including:

- ▶ The General Assembly of the European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO) in Helsinki, 28-29 April 2022.
- ▶ The 29th National Ethics Council Forum (NEC Forum) in Paris, 12-13 May 2022.
- ▶ The annual meeting of the H2020 SwafS INCENTIVE project – “Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society”, 31 May 2022.
- ▶ The pre-congress session of the ENRIO 2023 Congress on Research Integrity Practice in Paris, 6 September 2023. Link to the poster area: <https://premc.org/enrio2023/conference-rooms/enrio-pre-congress-session-poster-area/>

4. Key findings

4.1 For the PRO-Ethics guidelines

Language can be a big barrier to citizen participation

Research and innovation funding organisations struggle to communicate in terms that make sense to lay people, and can often be a step behind citizen science. PRO-Ethics heard from ethics and research integrity experts that even with patient and public involvement (PPI) practices (well developed in medical settings), researchers struggle. Therefore, PRO-Ethics presents an opportunity to create a resource that is more accessible and useful to research funding and practising organisations, as well as ethics committees or research integrity bodies who may face similar dilemmas in bridging the gap in understanding.

Figure 1: Workshop discussions around the question of 'How might PRO-Ethics guidelines help your organisation?'

Specificity in use cases

Throughout engagement with research ethics committees and integrity bodies, PRO-Ethics has aimed to ensure workshops are mutually beneficial for participants and to the consortia’s objectives. As such, many engagements have looked to link PRO-Ethics’ work with existing ethical approaches used by national and international bodies. Yet, one finding was the need to be specific about the use cases in which PRO-Ethics’ framework would apply. It would be important to borrow from what already works in other scientific practices (for example the ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity) but differentiate the framework to the particular use cases of research funding organisations. PRO-Ethics

should also aim to produce a guide that can be applied to individual cases, rather than a strict code that is not adaptable given the pluralism of moral theories with regard to ethical assessment.

PRO-Ethics also learnt from research ethics and integrity experts that ensuring that the framework could be translated to different contexts would be highly dependent on concrete examples that both identified target groups could relate to. Therefore, keeping the PRO-Ethics framework high-level enough for use in a wide range of activities but still providing some specificity to ensure correct translation was a main takeaway.

Learning from existing frameworks/tools

Ethics compliance and appraisal tend to be closely aligned with legal standards and regulations, which serve a different purpose to the guidance the PRO-Ethics framework looks to achieve. Nonetheless, there is a lot that can be learnt from these existing frameworks. One way to do this is for PRO-Ethics to use terminology that aligns with existing bodies of work. For example, ‘citizens’ can include many different people and communities, and these groups can be involved actively or less so.

Similarly, practices such as those developed for many decades in citizen science and public participation, involving different groups and methods, offer a wealth of knowledge that PRO-Ethics can tap into and borrow from. An emphasis on how ethical practice has developed to fit different contexts such as ‘everyday ethics’ in social work or patient participation in medical research, play an important role to ensure that PRO-Ethics is not reinventing the wheel but also clarifying the specific gap it fills.

Figure 2: Workshop discussions related to the question ‘What responsibilities do you have in the research process to ensure ethical conduct?’

Differentiating between funding and performing bodies

When the first version of the PRO-Ethics guidelines was presented to research ethics and integrity experts, the Framework spoke to both funding and performing organisations as one. A clear finding from engagement with these same experts was that these two groups, while similar in some ways, had distinct differences that needed to be addressed. How a funding organisation might encourage ethical practice versus how a performing organisation might apply best ethical practice were two distinct things that should be treated as such. Naming the specific ways that the guidelines may be used differently, during different points in the research process, was therefore considered extremely important.

How can RECs use the ethics framework?

RECs could use the PRO-Ethics framework as a basis for the improvement of research ethics review procedures. Ethical review is first and foremost about ensuring the protection of research participants. Many guidelines exist to help RECs assess whether research participants in clinical trials and other research projects are being treated well. However, a challenge is that RECs are limited in their ability to effectively assess the ethical dimensions of community involvement, lay participation and other methods of engagement, as well as the societal, economic and environmental consequences of research. In this regard, the Ethics Framework is a valuable resource. It provides RECs with important questions and answers to consider on the topic of ethics and participation in research projects.

Relevance to research integrity

Regarding issues of research integrity, the ALLEA Code of Conduct emphasises the importance of respect not only for other researchers, but also research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment, as well as accountability for wider societal impacts. The Ethics Framework can be a useful starting point for operationalising these aspirations in research practice. Moreover, questions of authorship and integrity of scientific data production in participatory R&I need to be considered more thoroughly than they have hitherto been, due to the rise of citizen science and other participatory research. In that regard, the PRO-Ethics outputs offer practical examples to the more streamlined items of the Code of Conduct.

4.2 For the wider R&I and ethics ecosystem

Convergence and divergence between research ethics and integrity

The effects of participation on different phases of research were also considered. Much of the discussion raised further questions around how we untangle ethics from integrity, and whether the activities of research funding organisations really differ significantly from other scientific research practice. In many ways, research ethics and integrity have mutually reinforcing dimensions. When considering the inclusion of research funding and practise to both research ethics and integrity aspects, the same argument might also be made. Therefore, identifying ethical issues (derived from ethics committees and research integrity bodies) provides guidance for R&I processes, a reflection on implications, an enhancement of transparency and accountability, as well as better processes.

Figure 3: Workshop discussion on the question of 'Are the effects of participation on research integrity different across types of participation'?

Citizen participation just makes for better research

We heard from workshop participants that citizen involvement pushes the boundaries of scientific practice, while remaining grounded in the needs of people and communities. This ensures that despite difficulties in executing citizen participation, it is worth the benefits to both research and innovation. When consideration of ethical issues is undertaken early and in an anticipatory way to allow for deliberation, properly planned citizen participation across the different phases of research will greatly enrich all research and innovation practices.

Figure 4: Workshop discussion on the question of 'Under what conditions, if any, can participation create barriers to good scientific practice?'

System-shaping powers

Discussions around who the framework should serve arose multiple times, as the guidelines are not intended for use by citizens themselves. However, we heard that it is important to have guidelines that also support correct communication with citizens. While our target audience will not change, PRO-Ethics has aimed to ensure an accessible format for the guidelines that can support translation of principles for citizens and other non-experts. This links to the system-shaping role that research and innovation funding and practising agencies play. Setting the tone for what is expected of all involved at various stages of research phases, i.e. ethical consideration of participation, will be something that all actors can shape in their individual organisations and with others.

5. Reflections on the process

What went well

The workshops with research ethics committees and integrity bodies were instrumental in shaping the PRO-Ethics framework in ways that aligned with existing guidance and tools. The discussions helped to tease out where PRO-Ethics provided a new contribution and where it could reinforce existing best practices.

Engaging with research ethics committees and integrity bodies also helped sustainably build a community that was receptive to the final Framework and to championing the tool once made public. This was extremely important to maximise the impact of PRO-Ethics beyond research funding and practising organisations. It was also mutually beneficial to the experts from across Europe to engage with one another.

As a result of the longstanding knowledge of ethical practice, research ethics committees and integrity bodies were also a critical friend to PRO-Ethics, pushing the consortia to deliver on its objectives in a meaningful way. All workshop participants were engaged and posed critical reflections openly and honestly with the PRO-Ethics team. Again, other stakeholders who were also coming at the subject of ethical practice in research for the first time or with limited practical experience, could not have contributed in this same way. In addition, for the experts themselves PRO-Ethics provided a forum for critical reflection and debate on individual perspectives on ethical approaches.

What could have been improved and lessons learnt

The workshops were important spaces for open discussion but there may have been better ways to gather input directly on the Framework's development. In a way, the timing of having a draft version of the framework to share later in the PRO-Ethics project allowed for research ethics committees and integrity bodies to engage with the project's RFO partners designing and running their pilots directly. However, more occasions for direct input on the Framework and Guidelines could have been beneficial to ensure the final output served the needs for these experts as well as PRO-Ethics target group.

More planned engagement with the consortia could also have supported alignment in the language and approach to ethical practice. Some discussions appeared to steer towards a binary of what research funding and performing organisations were accountable for in terms of ethical participation of citizens, versus research ethics committees and integrity bodies. Greater symbiosis of how all actors contributed to ethical practice in the system of innovation would have been beneficial for the sustainability of relationships between these two groups, brought together under PRO-Ethics but who should remain engaged.

6. Conclusions and next steps

With the aim of building a community of research ethics and integrity bodies that was engaged in PRO-Ethics' progress, the workshops delivered effective spaces for dialogue, critical reflection and useful feedback. PRO-Ethics did a great job of engaging with experts from across Europe who brought both national and international expertise on ethical practice regarding citizen participation.

From the engagement, both in workshops and via interviews and other presentations, PRO-Ethics has been able to align its framework amongst existing resources and differentiate the contribution it makes. Important lessons on how to make the final outputs accessible, flexible to multiple contexts, while specific enough to be useful, were all the result of engagement with research ethics and integrity bodies who were extremely generous with their knowledge.

While some useful learning and case studies examples were shared back with representatives from RECs and RIOs, more could be done to embed PRO-Ethics in the practices and resources that support these institutions.

This work will continue through national embedding events and culminate in the planned final conference PRO-Ethics will host in October 2023. These activities will help to bridge the gaps that remain in building a sustainable community of research ethics and integrity bodies.

Annex: Lists of participating organisations

Workshop participants (June 2022)

Organisation	Location
NEM	Norway
ECSITE	Belgium
BAREC	Belgium
AKEK	Germany
ERCIM	France
TOBB	Turkey
University of Vilnius	Lithuania
French Office for Research Integrity	France
EC CHU Charleroi	Belgium
INSERM	France
REC South East	Norway
LMU München	Germany
NVMETC Amsterdam	The Netherlands
Central European University	Austria
LBEC	Lithuania
CNBC	Cyprus
TUKIJA	Finland
University of Bonn	Germany
University of Tartu	Estonia
KEK	Switzerland
Czech Ethics Committees	Czech Republic
University of Neuchâtel (UNINE)	Switzerland
ONEP	Sweden
University of Maastricht	Netherlands
Danish National Center for Ethics	Denmark
EUREC Office	Germany

Workshop participants (September 2022)

Organisation	Location
Council of Finnish Academies	Finland
Office of the Ombudsperson for Academic Ethics and Procedures	Lithuania
Austrian Agency for Research Integrity	Austria
Health Research Board	Ireland
National Research Council	Italy
Finnish National Board on Research Integrity	Finland
UK Research Integrity Office	UK
French Office for Research Integrity	France
Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
ECSA - European Citizen Science Association	Germany
Team Scientific Integrity	Germany
ZSI	Austria
Nesta	UK
Innoviris	Belgium
VDI/VDE-IT	Germany
RCL	Lithuania
RCN	Norway
FFG	Austria
EUREKA	Belgium
EUREC	Germany

Workshop participants (January 2023)

Organisation	Location
Council of Finnish Academies	Finland
INSERM	France
Health Research Board	Ireland
Vilnius University	Lithuania
Office of the Ombudsperson for Academic Ethics and Procedures	Lithuania
CEIC	Portugal
Austrian Agency for Research Integrity	Austria
TU Wien	Austria
ECSA	Germany
University of Tartu	Estonia
Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
Luxembourg Agency for Research Integrity	Luxembourg
University of Central Lancashire	United Kingdom
French Office For Research Integrity (OFIS)	France
Association of Medical Ethics Committees	Germany
ENRIO	Sweden
Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics	Cyprus
Nesta	United Kingdom
ZSI	Austria
EUREC	Germany
TUD	The Netherlands
SciencesPo	France
LBG	Austria

